

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.9

Report on development of the 'State of the Arctic Environment'
pilot service website

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**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package 4

Innovating user-driven Arctic Eurogeo pilot services

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Executive summary

The State of the Arctic Environment is an interactive pilot visualisation tool that combines pan-Arctic environmental indicators with Indigenous oral histories and knowledge to provide a more holistic view of environmental change in the region. The website demonstrates the potential of integrating multiple knowledge systems to offer a more complete picture of environmental change in the Arctic and to enhance the understanding, accessibility, and relevance of Arctic monitoring data.

Introduction

The Arctic PASSION project is described in more detail in the project website which is available at <https://arcticpassion.eu/>. The purpose of Arctic PASSION is creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. This implies integrating already existing observing systems in a system of systems approach as well addressing gaps in the current observing system. Arctic PASSION will generate data through the project implementation, but equally important is to map and establish access to already existing datasets in support of the pilot services and other activities of Arctic PASSION.

As part of Work Package 4 - INNOVATING USER-DRIVEN ARCTIC EUROGEO PILOT SERVICES, task 4.3 implements the Pilot Service “State of the Arctic Environment”. The ambition of this service is to provide up-to-date scientific and Indigenous observations, covering a broad range of indicators representing the state and evolution of the Arctic climate and environment, in an intuitive and easily understandable manner. Target groups are organisations and individuals living, working or contributing to management in and of the Arctic, as well as a generally interested public that wants to learn more about the changing state of climate and environment there.

Evolution of the pilot service

The work on this web service started with identifying and contacting a number of representatives for potential user groups, to get their input both on the choice of indicators to include and how to visually and otherwise present them. Video interviews (from which quality-controlled minutes were produced) have been held with representatives from a fisheries organization, Arctic cruise operators (tourism), insurance, environmental NGO, Arctic media, reindeer herder’s association and the EEA. A number of other organizations have been asked to provide written input or interviewed. The process of acquiring input at this early stage of development was somewhat difficult as it was hard for potential users to understand what we planned to develop without seeing a draft version of the service. We expect it will

be easier to attract dialogue and input from further interest groups when the web service is ready for launch. The process of consulting potential users is covered in an article that is available at <https://arcticpassion.eu/blog/PS3consultations>.

Many prospective users want to see high-resolution local and regional information in addition to the overviews provided by pan-Arctic data sets. The tourist industry representative indicated that the web service could be very useful as an educational tool. Some said that it would be interesting to see how the development (of climate/environment) in their living or working area was, compared to other Arctic areas. Most of the representatives supported the proposed layout of the web service, with a combination of map-based and time-series visualizations of change. Several of the interviewees expressed a willingness to be consulted further and be part of a long-term user advisory group. They can be contacted again when the service is ready to be launched.

The first trial version of the web service was ready in spring 2023 and was presented at the Arctic PASSION General Assembly in June 2023, for discussion and feedback from meeting participants including Indigenous representatives. Based on feedback from this meeting and follow-up discussions with WP4 leadership, a decision was made to spend much of the remaining efforts on identifying and curating relevant existing Indigenous knowledge. The original scope for the pilot service was to include such information also, but it was now decided to lift this to a level where Indigenous knowledge would be at least as prominent as sensor-based observations in the service, and for all indicators that are going to be added. It was decided to first focus on the two identified biological indicators (Bowhead + Caribou/Reindeer) with regard to finding and preparing relevant Indigenous knowledge that would significantly expand the information provided by the count-based science data. The rationale is that if we can do it well for these two more complex indicators (complex in terms of data coverage), we would have a model that will work also for the more straightforward indicators such as sea ice and snow.

Implementation

The web service was meant to include observational data both from remote sensing and in situ observations. From the beginning we worked in parallel on collecting readily available datasets with pan-Arctic coverage (from remote sensing, typically climate-type indicators such as sea ice) and more difficult ones – i.e. those collected through in situ sensors or by humans (e.g. vegetation, biological indicators). Most of those prospective indicators which are not available from remote sensing were found to not have pan-Arctic coverage and/or to have limited historical extent, rendering it difficult to portray evolution over time. So far, two published biological data sets with reasonably good pan-Arctic coverage have been identified for use in the service: Bowhead/Greenland whale and caribou/reindeer. They were chosen also based on the feedback from the Indigenous knowledge holders given their relevance and prominence as a culturally relevant and significant species, even if many Indigenous communities stress the need to move beyond species-focus in discussions of the environment in the Arctic.

In 2024 and 2025 we carried out three parallel workflows:

1. collecting and processing sensor-based observational data across a suite of variables
2. preparing Indigenous materials for the two selected pilot biological indicators
3. redesigning the website, which has been built on WordPress, to better accommodate regional Indigenous information.

At the time of writing this report, the service provides eight indicators divided into four categories or 'spheres': Cryosphere, Marine, Terrestrial and Atmosphere. More details about data sources and their temporal and spatial resolution will be found on the web service. The following indicators are now included:

- ice extent,
- snow cover,
- number of snow days,
- near-surface air temperature,
- precipitation,
- Bowhead whales,
- *Rangifer sp.* (caribou/wild tundra and forest reindeer) and
- walruses.

For the two latter the service also provides map-referenced Indigenous knowledge. We are working on quality assurance of both the short descriptives texts for all sensor-based data sets (and reference materials for them) and for the Indigenous knowledge. These descriptions will be made available on the web site.

In the following we show some example screenshots from the service.

Climate Change in the Arctic

It is no surprise that Arctic landscapes are warming faster than the rest of the planet due to climate change – 4 times faster, according to the latest research! Climate change is having dramatic impacts on both the environment and the people who call the Arctic home.

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Discover more about what is happening in the Arctic by exploring a life on land (Terrestrial), life in the sea (Marine), atmospheric changes (Atmosphere), and trends in snow and ice (Cryosphere). The biosphere contains all the living parts of our planet – from the largest whales to microscopic algae. Life on land is quite a bit different than life underwater, so we have split this into two sections: "Terrestrial" and "Marine". Birds can be found in both!

For the first time, this website brings together scientific data and oral histories from Indigenous Peoples to offer a more complete picture of environmental change in the Arctic. By placing these two knowledge systems side by side, we aim to deepen our understanding of the shifts taking place across the region: ecologically, climatically, and culturally.

The oral histories included here represent just a small sample of a much larger body of Indigenous knowledge that exists. The oral histories shared with us reflect deeply rooted, place-based and lived experiences that span generations. This site gives a sense of what could be possible if services like this were expanded and used more widely to share and connect different sources of knowledge.

We are honoured and deeply grateful to the Indigenous People who have shared their knowledge, and we acknowledge that this information is shared with consent wherever possible. We recognise the responsibility that comes with sharing this knowledge and aim to do so with respect, care, and transparency.

Click on a "sphere" on the map to get started.

OUR NEWS

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Arctic PASSION

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Figure 1: Homepage of the website, featuring an introduction to the project and an interactive map that links to the four environmental spheres: cryosphere, terrestrial, marine and atmosphere (see fig. 2 for more detail).

Figure 2: The home page map is divided into four spheres: cryosphere, marine, terrestrial, atmosphere. Each sphere changes colour when hovered over, and clicking on a sphere takes the user to the corresponding page of the website. In the example here the user has selected cryosphere.

Figure 3: Cryosphere page map displaying the indicators sea ice minimum and number of snow days. Users can interactively select which dataset and time period to view from the available options. The map currently displays the decadal anomaly in the number of snow days for 2010-2020, referenced against the 1995-2020 period. The sea ice minimum extent for the year 2024 is also shown. The snow day anomaly is color-coded to represent the degree of deviation from the average. The sea ice extent is outlined with a border, allowing for visual comparisons of changes in minimum sea ice extent across different years.

Figure 4: Terrestrial page map showing the range of *Rangifer sp.* in green, snow cover in white, settlements in orange and oral histories in brown. Clicking on an oral history link will take the user to the full text of that entry at the bottom of the webpage, such as those illustrated in fig. 6.

Figure 5: Atmosphere page map displaying indicators for temperature and precipitation. The map currently shows temperature anomalies (°C) for the decade 2010–2020. The colour scale indicates the degree of deviation from the reference period: Very warm (darkest red) represents the highest positive anomalies; warm, slightly warm, (progressively lighter shades) represent decreasing positive anomalies or near-average temperatures; and cold, very cold (light to dark blue, not shown here) would indicate negative anomalies if present.

Gwich'in Climate Events Database

The Gwich'in are one of the most northerly Indigenous peoples of North America, living at the northwestern edge of the boreal forest. They are part of the Athapaskans family of Indigenous Peoples. At the time of contact with Euro-Canadians, their territory extended from Alaska's interior across the Yukon and into the Mackenzie Valley. Today, most Gwich'in live in the communities of Fort McPherson, Tsiigehtchic, Aklavik and Inuvik, though many families continue to use seasonal camps outside their communities. Hunting, fishing and trapping are still central to the community, both culturally and economically, with caribou, moose and whitefish being key staples of the Gwich'in diet.

The oral histories shared here come from a collection of testimonies from Gwich'in Elders and reflect their observations of climate, ecological and cultural changes across their traditional territory, from the 1900s to present day. This collection was curated by Prof. Leslie McCartney, an anthropologist and long-term research partner of the Gwich'in Tribal Council Department of Culture and Heritage, on behalf of the Gwich'in Tribal Council Department of Culture and Heritage. This database categorises data from the vast archives of Gwich'in oral history and ecological knowledge. Prof. McCartney and University of Michigan research intern, Nolan Loftis, reviewed transcripts, coded caribou events into an "event database" categorised by decade.

Some key observations taken from the oral histories and their significance is shown as a pop up where relevant.

[Hide References](#)

Unalakleet Oral Histories

Mustonen, T., Van Dam, B., 2021. Climate Change and Unalakleet: A Deep Analysis. Sustainability 13: 9971. [Link](#)

Mustonen, T., Mustonen, K., 2009. It Has Been in Our Blood for Years and Years that We Are Salmon Fishermen – A Book of Oral History from Unalakleet, Alaska, USA. Waasa Graphics Oy, Vaasa Finland. [Link](#)

Gwich'in Oral Histories

Website: Gwich'in Tribal Council, Department of Culture and Heritage and the Snowchange Cooperative, 2024. Gwich'in Climate Events Database. ArcGIS StoryMaps. [Link](#)

Figure 6: Screenshot from terrestrial page showing introductory text to the Gwich'in Indigenous people who have provided their oral histories for the website, followed by references with links to access further information or more data.

Steve Ivanoff: "You know, like the last couple of years, we haven't had the caribou down here, like we did within the last decade. And, and we've adapted to that. You know, with alternative food sources."

Jerry Ivanoff

"My caribou steak tastes better than the beef, that's sure and [the meat] has been aging for four months. My caribou meat, I take it out, and cut it up. And the first one I feed them, my dog. And the next one I cut up, they are all good. They are all red meat, and fresh, and real good meat."

Jolene Nanouk Katchatag

"Beluga and caribou migrations have changed since 2002."

Iyengra Evenki Oral Histories, Southern Sakha-Yakutia, Siberia

Anonymous female reindeer herder: Spring is the season of a new life. New calves come into this world. For us, for Evenki, this is the happiest and the most exciting season. Reindeer calving is very important for it increases the number of reindeer. There are domestic and wild reindeer. Today we will talk about hunting of wild reindeer. In past, long time ago when I was a child, out reindeer herd was located about 110 kilometres away from the settlement. An all-terrain-vehicle delivered food two or three times a year. That is why, our main food was wild reindeer meat. There was enough wild reindeer in the area both for us and for other predators (wolves, bears, etc). There was enough wild reindeer. We harvested as much as **Sevek**² would give us—Evenki do not take too much, they have to share with others—**Nimat**³. Sometimes in the morning you would come out of your tent and reindeer were going in circles and were jumping away from something within **kure**⁴—turned out that a w... process of sharing harvested animal with others (a ritual) ... deer. Nowadays, it does not happen often. In the course of time, the climate has changed—fires, droughts. Because of the fires the number of wolves an... d away wild reindeer and got at our domestic reindeer. We had to move closer to the settlement. At present there are horrible times for reindeer herders. **Gold-diggers are everywhere**, destroying the land. But reindeer have to eat lichen and drink clean water. Everywhere is the noise of machines, there are no wild reindeer left, they migrated to pristine areas. Because there is no wild reindeer, Evenki food supply is disrupted. In summer, if you are lucky, you can harvest one wild reindeer and the probability of it is 1 to 100. And in winter, reindeer herders go away for a month in order to harvest some meat for their families. When gold-diggers have appeared, nothing alive was left in the forest.

Figure 7: Example showing oral histories on wild forest reindeer. Hovering over highlighted sections of the oral histories reveals explanatory text boxes to provide user with a meaning or additional context.

Connected with the work on Pilot Service 3 in Arctic PASSION, a more detailed Sea ice service has been created and delivered (see Deliverable report 4.4 – Regional sea ice tool). This is a stand-alone service that is available online (<https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index>). It provides an example of how the whole ‘State of the Arctic Environment’ web service could be expanded with more detail and functionality in the future, if 1) there is a user need for it, 2) sufficient resources become available, and 3) improved data coverage becomes available for additional indicators.

The full pilot web service is still on a password-protected website. This is both due to the service still not being complete in terms of a sufficient number of indicators and because we are finalizing the quality assurance process in collaboration with Indigenous community representatives. It is important that this process is completed respectfully and thoroughly before a public launch.

Future perspectives

We will continue to work on populating and quality controlling the pilot web service until the end of the project period (December 2025). We plan to add permafrost and possibly additional indicators before the end of the project, depending on how time-consuming each indicator is. We plan to launch the web site no later than December 2025.

The methods for processing and displaying the data within the web service will be published as a citable methods package on Zenodo before the end of the project, with a link added to the web service.

At the time of writing this report, personnel and funding were not in place for the partners to continue development of the pilot service after the closure of the Arctic PASSION project. GRIDA is committed to maintaining the web site for at least one year after the end of Arctic PASSION. All pilot service partners see the value and further potential of the service and will actively seek funding for 1) further maintenance and 2) further development. The latter will include both adding more indicators and more Indigenous observations to the indicators that are now in place.

The feedback from Indigenous representatives and knowledge holders that have been involved in curation and quality control of the web service is that they are very happy with their observations being shown in the service. When that knowledge is made available together and on equal footing with scientific data, there is great potential to build and convey a better and more complete understanding of the ongoing changes in the Arctic climate and environment. The species have been chosen to reflect the culturally and ecologically central species even if many Indigenous knowledge holders report that the emphasis on species is not reflective of the holistic Indigenous worldviews, cosmologies or knowledge systems. However, in this case both the bowhead whale and the wild reindeer/caribou are indicators of the ecosystem health in terms of large spatial areas and reflect a specific and significant Indigenous interest and cultural links.

We suggest that a new round of consultations with prospective user group representatives is carried out before substantial effort is made both for finalizing a more comprehensive service and setting up an apparatus for long-term service and updating.

